

Minutes EB25-3
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
2 September 2025 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apologies

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Resignation of Anna-Louise Reysenbach
Amendment of a SeqCode recommendation

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved. Completed*
- PH to request the ISME Board to allow ISME funding to be used as stipends to students. Ongoing, ISME office indicated that an application for 2026 needs to be submitted ASAP.*
- PH to inform ISME that we are grateful that they will take over the administration of the SeqCode prize. Completed*
- LMR to split the training video into two and the links to be shared with the wider community. Completed*
- FV to circulate the draft a text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode amongst the EB. Text was circulated, now needs to be submitted to Wikipedia.*
- KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries. Ongoing*
- Dialog between the ICSP, BISMIS and the SeqCode. FV to request Bergey's Manual Trust to initiate the establishment of a representative organization committee for the proposed meeting between the different parties.*
- Update on ISME Communications-Taxonomy. The establishment of this initiative was announced in ISME Communications (<https://doi.org/10.1093/ismeco/ycaf106>).*

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

A draft manuscript proposing amendments to the SeqCode, introducing the ability to designate strains as paratypes, has been circulated. An updated version will be shared soon and comments are requested by 15 September. FV will request ISME to consider waiving the publication costs of such manuscripts in ISME Communications.

Standards Working Group

The working group is in the process of discussing the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries of genome sequences as well as the need to specify quality requirements for genomes obtained from isolates.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 1057 names have been validated, which include those of 578 species. The genus *Skiveiella* was the 1000th name validly published under the SeqCode.

The registry deals with around 2000 visitors per month and they represent a wide geographic distribution. The option to create a Wikispecies or Wikidata page linked to the Registry has been implemented. A link to the registry for reviewers to check the data of proposed taxa during the review process is also available. A paper providing practical guidance on the naming of MAGs by Ernster and Rodriguez-R has been published in the special SeqCode issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0723202025000657>)

Reconciliation Commission

No update.

5. New Meeting link

With the move of LMR to Aalborg University the current link used for EB meetings will no longer be available. A new link using Microsoft Teams will be established. All data related to the registry and the SeqCode have also been moved, including the link to RocketChat.

6. Changes to the SeqCode

Possible changes to Recommendation 9.2 of the SeqCode requesting that new names should differ by at least three characters needs to be reviewed as it potentially dissuades authors from forming useful names and some names are already contra to this recommendation. This suggestion will be incorporated in the same manuscript proposing the introduction of paratypes.

7. Resignation of the Vice Chair

ALR indicated that she would like to step down. This was reluctantly accepted and her contribution to the SeqCode noted by the Executive. A request for nominations will be made as part of the next newsletter to the SeqCode community. Once nominations have been received a formal election process will be initiated to appoint the next vice chair. ALR will continue to serve as vice-chair until the new person is elected.

8. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. FV to upload the SeqCode Wikipedia page.
3. LMR and BW to prepare and submit a funding application for 2026 to the ISME office.
4. BW to prepare an updated manuscript to propose changes to the SeqCode. The updated SeqCode manuscript will be circulated and members are to respond by 15 September.
5. FV to request nominations for the vice- chair position as part of the next newsletter to the SeqCode community.

Ongoing items

6. PH to request the ISME Board to allow ISME funding to be used as stipends to students.
7. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.
8. FV to request ISME to consider waiving the publication costs of manuscripts related to the operation of the SeqCode in ISME Communications.
9. FV to request Bergey's Manual Trust to initiate the establishment of a representative organization committee for the proposed meeting between the ICSP and SeqCode

Minutes prepared by FV: 8 September 2025

Approved: 15 September 2025